

A STUDY ON THE PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF ECO-FRIENDLY BRICK MASONRY AS FILLER SLAB

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Abstract. Filler Slab roofs are designed using the same principles as conventional Reinforced Cement Concrete (RCC) slabs, but replace part of the concrete in the tensile zone with alternative materials like eco-friendly, locally available bricks. These Filler Slabs experience durability issues, such as crack formation, similar to normal concrete. However, the incorporation of microorganisms to induce self-healing properties in building materials, including brick making, presents a viable solution to these issues. This paper explores the use of microbial bricks to reduce seepage and efflorescence in RC Filler Slabs, enhancing sustainability in roof structures. The Filler Slab approach can be applied to housing projects to achieve cost-effectiveness and structural stability without compromising on strength and durability. By using lightweight filler materials, approximately 30-35% of concrete and 25% of overall costs can be saved. This method also leverages the benefits of brick masonry, including high compressive strength, fire resistance, and thermal and acoustic performance.

Keywords: Filler Slab, Microbial Bricks, Self-Healing Properties, Cost-Effectiveness

Annotatsiya. To'ldiruvchi plitalar tomlari an'anaviy Temir-beton (RCC) plitalari bilan bir xil printsiplardan foydalangan holda ishlab chiqilgan, ammo kuchlanish zonasida betonning bir qismini ekologik toza, mahalliy g'isht kabi muqobil materiallar bilan almashtiring. Ushbu plomba plitalari odatdagi betonga o'xshash yoriqlar paydo bo'lishi kabi chidamlilik muammolariga duch keladi. Biroq, qurilish materiallarida, jumladan, g'isht ishlab chiqarishda o'z-o'zini davolash xususiyatlarini qo'zg'atish uchun mikroorganizmlarning qo'shilishi bu muammolarni hal qilishning maqbul echimini taqdim etadi. Ushbu maqola RC to'ldiruvchi plitalardagi sızıntı va gullashni kamaytirish, tom tuzilmalarida barqarorlikni oshirish uchun mikrobial g'ishtlardan foydalanishni o'rganadi. To'ldiruvchi plita yondashuvi mustahkamlik va chidamlilikka putur etkazmasdan iqtisodiy samaradorlik va tizimli barqarorlikka erishish uchun uy-joy loyihalariga qo'llanilishi mumkin. Engil plomba materiallari yordamida betonning taxminan 30-35% va umumiy xarajatlarning 25% ni tejash mumkin. Bu usul, shuningdek, yuqori bosim kuchi, yong'inga chidamlilik va termal va akustik ishlashni o'z ichiga olgan g'ishtli toshning afzalliklaridan foydalanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Plomba plitasi, mikrobial g'ishtlar, o'z-o'zini davolash xususiyatlari, iqtisodiy samaradorlik.

Аннотация. Крыши из наполнительных плит спроектированы с использованием тех же принципов, что и обычные железобетонные плиты (RCC), но часть бетона в зоне растяжения заменяется альтернативными материалами, такими как экологически чистые, доступные на месте кирпичи. Эти плиты-наполнители испытывают проблемы с долговечностью, такие как образование трещин, как и обычный бетон. Однако включение микроорганизмов для придания свойств самовосстановления в строительные материалы, в том числе при производстве кирпича, представляет собой жизнеспособное решение этих проблем. В этой статье исследуется использование микробных кирпичей

для уменьшения просачивания и высолов в железобетонных плитах-наполнителях, что повышает устойчивость кровельных конструкций. Подход «Наполнительная плита» может применяться в жилищных проектах для достижения экономической эффективности и структурной устойчивости без ущерба для прочности и долговечности. Используя легкие наполнители, можно сэкономить примерно 30-35% бетона и 25% общих затрат. Этот метод также использует преимущества кирпичной кладки, в том числе высокую прочность на сжатие, огнестойкость, тепловые и акустические характеристики.

Ключевые слова: плита-наполнитель, микробные кирпичи, свойства самовосстановления, экономическая эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

Filler slab technology has been a part of India's architectural landscape for a long time, evolving in various forms. Indo-British architect Laurie Baker, renowned for his sustainable architecture and green building practices, notably popularized this technique in South India, particularly in Kerala^[4,1]. During a certain period, Baker's unique style was so influential that many aspired to construct "Baker model homes." His revolutionary approach, even as early as the 1960s, focused on rainwater harvesting, minimizing the use of energy-consuming materials, and building homes that harmonize with the site and environment^[3,12].

In a developing country like India, where only 20% of the population belongs to the highest-paid group, affordable housing remains a critical issue. Affordable housing, defined as housing that costs up to 30% of a low- or middle-income family's income, is often inaccessible to the low-income group. Addressing this challenge requires reducing construction costs through better management, efficient use of local resources, skills, and technologies without compromising building energy efficiency and health standards^[8]. In recent years, the green building movement has gained momentum, with builders and homeowners exploring innovative construction methods to reduce energy costs. The use of low-cost building materials in housing construction enhances accessibility for low-income groups. Efficient planning and the adoption of technologies like filler slab construction can make housing more affordable, sustainable, and structurally sound^[10].

Filler Slab: Filler slab technology is a cost-effective and innovative method for building slabs. It reduces the slab's dead load by replacing some of the concrete with filler materials, often local and eco-friendly ones. This approach saves on both concrete and steel, making it greener depending on the filler material used. A filler slab is a type of construction where part of the concrete at the bottom is replaced with filler material. This technique reduces the weight of the slab while keeping its strength. The slabs are cast on-site like normal slabs. Formwork is laid, and reinforcement bars (rebars) are placed according to design. Usually, a maximum spacing of 300 mm is adopted, though wider spacing can be used if the design allows^[16]. Shown in Fig: 1

Fig.1. Filler slab

The concept is based on the fact that concrete is only needed in the upper part of the slab for compression. The filler material in the lower part doesn't contribute to the slab's structural integrity but reduces its weight and cost. Filler slabs also provide aesthetic benefits, as the filler material can be left exposed to create pleasing patterns on the ceiling. Proper planning and design ensure the slab's structural integrity, avoiding cracks and leaks with good workmanship. The structural design of filler slabs is similar to conventional slabs, and they can be designed as one-way or two-way slabs depending on the support conditions. Accurate load calculations are essential to benefit from the reduced weight. In summary, filler slab technology is an efficient way to build strong, lightweight, and aesthetically pleasing slabs while saving on materials and costs^[10,14,11].

Materials Used in Filler Slab Construction

- ❖ Mangalore tiles
- ❖ Claypans
- ❖ Bricks
- ❖ Waste bottles
- ❖ Coconut shells
- ❖ Thermocol
- ❖ Cyber wastes (e.g., keyboards)
- ❖ Stabilized mud blocks

In this project, bricks are used. Bricks are construction materials made primarily from clay, used to build walls, pavements, and other elements in masonry. Clay bricks are produced by drying and firing clay or shale, forming a porous structure^[14].

Advantages of Filler Slabs^[16]

1. **Cost-effective:** 20% cheaper than traditional RCC slabs due to cheaper filler materials and reduced steel and concrete use.
2. **Thermal insulation:** Provides great thermal insulation due to air pockets formed by the contours of the tiles.
3. **Heat resistance:** Offers pleasant living room temperatures, especially in hot and humid climates.
4. **Waste management:** Reuses waste materials like keyboards and bottles, reducing environmental impact.
5. **Reduced carbon footprint:** Decreases carbon footprint by 20%.
6. **Aesthetic appeal:** Enhances ceiling appearance with the right filler patterns.

MATERIALS COLLECTED: The constituent materials used in the investigation are Ordinary Portland cement, water, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate and bricks were collected from local sources^[12].

Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC): OPC 43 cement shall conform to IS: 8112-1989 and the designed strength of 28 days shall be minimum 43 MPa or 430 kg /sq cm. Shown in fig 2. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) 43 Grade is a premium quality cement manufactured from world renowned Nazi limestone. Made using next generation German Technology, the 43 Grade cement develops high early strength as well as high ultimate strength. This grade of cement is the most popular cement used in the country today. OPC 43 is used for general RCC construction where the grade of concrete is up to M30^[4]. In this experimental study the Cement used for casting of the specimens based Ordinary Portland Cement with 43grade is conforming to IS 8112-1989. The chemical component are shown in fig 2 and shown in table 1.

Fig:2: Ordinary Portland Cement

Table1: Chemical composition of OPC

Chemical Analysis	CaO	SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	Al ₂ O ₃	SO ₃	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O
Mass %	66.33	18.6	4.03	3.77	2.67	2.13	1.39	0.46

Water: Water used for mixing and curing shall be clean and free from oils, acids, alkalis, salts, sugar, organic materials or other substances that may be deleterious to concrete. Portable water is generally considered satisfactory for mixing concrete^[5]. The water pH level in 7. The chemical and physical properties are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Chemical and physical properties of water

Properties	Molecular weight	Melting point(K)	Boiling point(K)	Density	Viscosity
Value	18.015	273.0	373.0	0.997	0.890

Fine Aggregate

Fine aggregate is 40% out of total aggregate in concrete. fine aggregate size as per is code 383 is 4.75mm,2.36mm,1.18mm, 600-micron, 300 micron,150 micron. so, all type of particle size in aggregate. The sand used for this study was locally procured and conformed to grading zone III as per BIS: 383-2007. The sand was sieved through a standard sieve size of 4.75 mm sieve to remove any particles greater than 4.75 mm and then was washed to remove the dust^[6]. Fine aggregates are used in projects where a smooth yet highly compacted surface is desired. Fine aggregates are ideal for use underneath pavers, path fines, track fines, athletic infield material and can even be used as a soil amendment. The physical properties are shown in table 3.

Table 3 Physical properties of fine aggregate

Properties	Type	Specific Gravity	Density	Fineness modulus
Value	Manufactured	2.63	1620 Kg/m ³	2.39

Bricks: Bricks are construction materials used to build walls, pavements, and other masonry elements. Traditionally, bricks are made from clay, but they can also be made from other materials or chemically cured construction blocks^[7]. The physical properties of bricks are shown in table 4.

Standard Brick Sizes (IS 1077):	
1.	190 x 90 x 90 mm
2.	190 x 90 x 40 mm

Relevant Standards:
IS 1077: Common burnt clay building bricks.
IS 2212 – 1991: Code of practice for brickwork, which deals with clay brick masonry construction and the erection of clay brick walls.

Table 4 Physical Properties of bricks

Physical Properties	Density	Water absorption	Initial rate of suction	Compressive strength
Value	2268Kg/m ³	4.1	0.512	133.8 N/mm ²

METHODS OF FILLER SLAB MAKING:

Size of specimen and mould: The cube specimen is 600mm x450mm x100mm size, the mould are made of wood and made to enable easy removal of the specimens from the mould are placed on a metal box plate having a plain surface. A tamping bar of 16mm diameter steel 0.6 m long with a bullet pointed out is used for tamping^[6]. Shown in fig 3.

Fig: 3: Size of specimen and mould

Mixing: The materials are mixed using mixer machine. when the mixing drum is changed by powder loader all mixing water shall be introduced into the drum before the solid materials the skip shall be loaded with about one half of the coarse aggregate, then with the fine aggregate then with cement and finally remaining coarse aggregate on top^[7]. Mixing shall not be less than 2 minutes. Shown in fig 4.

Placing: The material obtained from the mixer machine and bricks are filled into the mould, before the initial setting time the mixture should be placed^[17]. Shown in fig 4.

Curing: The test specimen are stored in moist air for 24 hours and after this period the specimens are marked and removed from the mould and kept submerged in clean fresh water until testing. Shown in fig 4. The slab is placed for curing under 7days, 14 days. Shown in Fig 4^[9]

Fig:4: Mixing, Placing, and Curing

MIX RATIO:

Table 5. Mix Ratio

Cement	Water	Fine Aggregate	Coarse Aggregate	W/C Ratio
551.2 kg/m ³	220.48kg/m ³	641.3 kg	1087.7 kg	0.40
1	0.4	1.16	2	0.40

TESTING FOR MATERIALS

Specific gravity for cement^[16]: The specific gravity of cement is determined using the Le-chatelier apparatus according to IS269:1989. Here's how it works: First, the apparatus is washed, cleaned, and dried. Then, it is weighed (W1g). About 100g of cement is added to the apparatus, which is weighed again (W2g). Kerosene is added up to the hole of the cone, and the combined weight of the kerosene and cement is recorded (W3g). After that, the apparatus is emptied, cleaned, filled with only kerosene, and weighed once more (W4g). The specific gravity of the cement is then calculated using a formula based on these measurements. **Specific gravity of cement = 3.13.**

Consistency Test of Cement^[13]: The consistency test is essential for determining the amount of water needed to achieve standard consistency in cement. This consistency is crucial for other tests like compressive strength and setting time. For the test, take 400 grams of OPC cement and add 118 grams of water (29.5% of the cement weight). Mix thoroughly and let it sit for 3-5 minutes. Place the mould under the Vicat apparatus, remove the plunger, and let it penetrate the paste. After 3 seconds, note the reading on the Vicat scale. Noted in table 6.

Table 6: Consistency Test of Cement^[10]

Trial no	Weight of cement (g)	% of water(ml)	Amount of water (ml)	Pointer reading from bottom
1.	400	30	90	18
2.	400	31	93	10
3.	400	32	96	8
4.	400	33	99	5

Consistency of cement = 33%

Initial setting time of cement^[22]: Initial setting time of cement is defined as the time elapsed between the moments when water is added to the cement to the time when the cement paste starts losing its plasticity. It can also be defined as the time elapsed between the moments when water is added to the cement to the time when the Vicat square needle penetrates a depth of 33-35 mm from the top (5 to 7 mm from the bottom) of the mould of the Vicat Apparatus. The readings are noted in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Initial Setting Time of Cement

SI.No	Time In Minutes	Pointer Reading From Bottom
1.	0	0
2.	5	0
3.	10	1
4.	15	1.5
5.	20	2
6.	25	4
7.	30	5

Initial setting time = 30 minutes

Sieve Analysis of Fine Aggregate^[11]: The sieve analysis test helps determine the size distribution of aggregate particles to ensure they meet design and production standards. Take a 2kg sample of coarse aggregate. Arrange the IS sieves in descending order: 80mm, 40mm, 20mm, 10mm, 4.75mm, and 2.36mm. Pour the sample into the top sieve (80mm) and sieve for 10 minutes. After sieving, weigh the aggregates retained on each sieve and record the weights. This process ensures the aggregates meet the necessary specifications. The readings are noted in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Sieve Analysis of Fine Aggregate^[6]

IS Sieve size	The weight retained (Gm)	Percent weight retained	Cumulative percent of weight retained	Cumulative percent of passing
4.75mm	18	1.8	1.8	98.2
2mm	165	16.5	18.3	81.7
1mm	227	22.7	41	59
600μ	340	34	75	25
300μ	150	15	90	10
0.150	80	8	98	2
pan	20	2	100	0
Total	1000		424.1	

Fineness of fine aggregate = 4.24

Sieve analysis of coarse aggregate^[8]: A 1kg dry sample of coarse aggregate was sieved using IS sieve sizes of 20mm, 12.5mm, 11.2mm, 10mm, 4.75mm, and a pan. The material retained in each sieve was collected and weighed. The percentage of coarse aggregate passing through each sieve was calculated and recorded. The results were then compared with the grading limits chart (IS 2386-part I) to determine the actual zone of the coarse aggregate, as shown in Table 9

Table 9: Sieve analysis of coarse aggregate

IS Sieve Size (mm)	Weight retained (gm)	% weight retained	Cumulative percent of weight retained	Cumulative percentage of passing
80	0	0	0	100
40	98	98	4.9	95.1
20	1590	1688	84.4	15.6
10	305	1993	99.65	0.35
4.75	7	2000	100	0
2.36	0	-	100	-
Total	2000		788.95	

$$\text{Fineness modulus of Coarse Aggregate} = \text{Cumulative \% of weight retained}/100$$

$$= 788.95/100$$

$$\text{Fineness modulus of Coarse Aggregate} = 7.88$$

RESULT AND DISCUSSION: This standard provides the guide lines for proportioning concrete mixes as per the requirements using the concrete making materials including ether supplementary materials identified for this purpose, the proportioning is carried out to achieve specified characteristics at specified age, workability of fresh concrete and durability requirements. This standard is applicable for ordinary and standard concrete grades only, all requirements of IS 456 in So far as they apply, shall be deemed to form part of this standard. As per code book IS 516-1959 Methods of Tests for Strength of filler slab. Mould made up of wooden mould with size 600mmx450mmx100mm. shown in fig: 5^[15]

Fig:5: Specimen Mould size 600 x 450 x 100mm

Experimental Results of Flexural Strength^[12] : The test was carried out as per IS 516 : 1959. The specimen of size 150mm,150mm,700mm was thick concrete of various concrete mixtures were cast to test under flexural testing machine. The specimen after demolding were

stored in curing tank and on removal of specimen from water the flexure test was conducted at 14 days and the results are represents in Table 10, flow chart shown in below and comparison of cost analysis for conventional slab and filler slab shown in table 11.

Table 10: Flexural strength in 14 days

Sl.No	Mix	Flexural Strength N/mm ²
1	Conventional Slab	3.7
2	Filler Slab	3.9

Flow chart for Flexural Strength in 14 Days.

Table 11: Comparison of Cost Analysis for Conventional slab and Filler Slab^[7, 8]

Sl.No	Item	Cost for Conventional Slab	Cost for Filler Slab
1	Concrete, Including Labor	1650	773
2	Brick	-	224
3	Reinforcement	1800	1600
4	Steel Cutting, Bending	1450	1250
5	Mason (2 nd class)	1500	1100
	Total	6400/-	4948/-
	Savings	22.68%	

CONCLUSION: Filler slab construction is a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative to conventional RC slabs. This method reduces construction costs by using fewer building materials and utilizing innovative techniques. Filler slabs save on cement and steel, and they are suitable for soils with low bearing capacity. They maintain similar flexural strength to conventional slabs, while also providing better thermal insulation and aesthetic appeal. Additionally, using filler slabs can lead to significant cost savings, approximately 22%, and a reduction in concrete use by 25%. This technique not only enhances the building's appearance but also contributes to sustainability by reducing the overall carbon footprint and reusing waste materials^[16].

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